

A Review of Educational Interventions Effect on The Level of Emotional Intelligence Among Undergraduate Nursing Students

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Abstract

Background:

Emotional intelligence (E-I) combines various abilities, including self-awareness, self-regulation, empathy, social skills, and motivation. These competencies are particularly crucial for nursing students, enabling them to cope with high-pressure circumstances effectively. Given the dynamic nature of the healthcare environment and the evolving needs of patients, a strong E-I from nursing professionals is needed. Therefore, the focus of nursing education has shifted to enhancing these skills. This review study is very significant for the nursing sector, both academically and clinically. It examined a number of studies, including different educational interventions, strategies, approaches and methods to strengthen the E-I levels of undergraduate nursing students and highlighted how these interventions and methods affect nursing students and the nursing profession. Importantly, it also identified areas that need further research, sparking curiosity and interest in potential future studies. **Methodology:** It involved conducting a literature review by searching several databases, including Pub-Med, Bio-Med Central, Pak-MediNet, CABI, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. The review includes only those studies published between 2014 and 2024, limiting the criteria to those focused on educational interventions and methods to improve E-I levels among undergraduate nursing students. Data were gathered and analysed to determine the most successful approaches and results related to E-I enhancement. **Result:** The review findings specify that several methods and educational approaches significantly advanced E-I among undergraduate nursing students. Numerous studies have shown that different techniques, including programs focused on mindfulness, training focused on developing and enhancing emotional skills, practice based on reflection, workshops based on interpersonal and social communication, and learning through simulation, had

successfully improved E-I of the nursing students in both clinical and academic contexts. these advancements improve quality patient care and help prevent nursing students' professional burnout. *Conclusion:* Various methods and educational strategies have successfully boosted the E-I of nursing students. This is necessary because it promotes and develops the crucial skills needed for quality patient care and strengthens professional resilience. Continued a strong focus on special E-I training is necessary for the nursing profession.

Keywords:

Educational intervention, Effect, Emotional intelligence (E-I) level, Undergraduate nursing students.

Introduction:

Emotional intelligence (E-I) is a competency and a chunk of several skills that are increasingly acknowledged as crucial for nursing students, as it significantly influences their abilities to deliver empathetic care, handle challenging situations, and maintain their well-being (Salovey and Mayer, 2020; Mayer et al., 2016). E-I refers to the capability to recognise, utilise, understand, and manage one's and other people's feelings. This is a really needed skill for nursing students to possess, as it is required in both clinical and educational contexts (Singh et al., 2024; Sharma et al., 2023; Vanderriet et al., 2019; Goleman, 2015; Codier et al., 2014). The integration of E-I training into nursing education is absolutely necessary as nursing education continues to develop to fulfil the requirements of the diverse and modern healthcare environment (Cengiz et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 2023; Castelino and Mendonca, 2023; Kaddoura, 2020; Teskereci et al., 2020; Foster et al., 2018). Many studies revealed that different educational interventions and techniques focused on E-I could positively affect E-I in nursing students, lead to the best nursing care, decrease stress and increase overall well-being (Belay et al., 2021; Kuruvilla and Menezes, 2019; Gurkova and Zelenikova, 2018; Cox and Km, 2018; Birks et al., 2017; Orak et al., 2016). Some other studies suggested that we can improve nursing students' E-I capability through a number of educational interventions, such as simulation-based learning, mindfulness training and seminars (Raut and Gupta, 2021; Akerjordet and Severinsson, 2015). Although there is a difference between the impact of these interventions, comprehensive reviews still need to determine the best methods and areas that require more investigation (Taylor et al., 2022;

Moustakas and Constantinos, 2020). Therefore, this study aims to synthesise the current body of literature regarding educational interventions designed to improve the E-I levels of undergraduate nursing students between 2014 and 2024. This highlights the best methods and their effects on nursing student performance in both clinical and academic settings. This will help the nursing educator and stockholders to better prepare their students for the emotional demands of the nursing field. Which will eventually promote satisfaction and positive patient outcomes (Guo et al., 2019; Goudarzian et al., 2019).

Methods:

Search Strategy and Selection Process:

The researcher conducted a thorough search for relevant studies in this field utilised numerous electronic databases, including the Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Pub-Med, Bio-Med Central, Pak-MediNet (Medical Information Gateway of Pakistan), Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International (CABI), Google Scholar, and Research Gate. The researcher used a range of search terms, including "effect," "impact," "effectiveness," "emotional quotient," "emotional intelligence," "education," "undergraduate nurse," "nursing students," and "emotional quotient*," "EIQ*," and "E-I*". The articles were selected from open-access international, regional, and national journals in the last 10 years between 2014 and 2024 to ensure the inclusion of recent studies. Articles were written in English and specifically investigated or discussed the effect of educational intervention on undergraduate nursing students' E-I levels. Furthermore, that included experimental, quasi-experimental, or observational studies. Moreover, duplicate articles were removed to avoid redundancy. During the screening process, outdated articles were not considered. After screening, 48 articles meeting the inclusion criteria were selected for review.

Eligibility Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies published from 2014 through January 2024
- Studies published only in the English language
- Studies that included only nursing students

Exclusion Criteria:

- Studies that were published before 2014 and not in the English language
- Studies that included other students

Results:

The review uncovered 48 relevant articles published between 2014 and 2024. Most of the studies included in the review originated worldwide. To address our research question, we categorised the findings into five categories: (I) Programs focused on mindfulness, (II) Training focused on developing and enhancing emotional skills, (III) Practice based on reflection, (IV) Workshops based on interpersonal and social communication, and (V) learning through simulation. Each category has been discussed in more detail.

The Programs Focused on Mindfulness:

Studies have investigated how well-mindfulness-based interventions foster E-I in nursing students. A 2017 systematic review highlighted that nursing students' emotional awareness, empathy, and stress management abilities were greatly enhanced by intervention focused on mindfulness training (Birks et al., 2017). Likewise, a different study found that intervention focused on mindfulness improved students' capacity to control their emotions and stay cool under pressure in challenging situations (Foster et al., 2018; Winning and Ridderinkhof, 2017). A randomised controlled trial (RCT) conducted in 2021 further supports and validates the previous findings. According to the research findings, an intervention focused on mindfulness positively impacted students' E-I scores compared to the group that served as the control (Raut and Gupta, 2021). Furthermore, mindfulness programs based on thought reflection and yoga positively impacted nursing students' E-I levels. The result indicated a significant decline in stress and anxiety levels. This can enhance the overall mental health of nursing students (Batan, 2024; Taylor et al., 2023; Dugue et al., 2021).

The Training Focused on Developing and Enhancing Emotional Skills:

An interventional study was conducted in 2014 to see the impact of E-I education on nursing students' clinical performance. The result revealed a noteworthy positive

improvement in managing their and patients' emotions, social skills, and overall clinical performance (Codier et al., 2014). Another study conducted in 2015 emphasised the role of E-I in the nursing profession. The study revealed the benefits and growing demand for E-I training in nursing. Nursing programmes should teach E-I and its practical skills because integrating emotional skills into nursing education is much more needed (Akerjordet and Severinsson, 2015). Similarly, another study conducted in 2019 to check the E-I and academic delay revealed that nursing students who participated in a training focused on E-I skills and abilities benefited from the training. Participants who took part reported low levels of depression and enhanced overall satisfaction (Guo et al., 2019). E-I skills are commonly acknowledged as a fundamental factor of nursing education, frequently referred to as the heart of nursing (Teskereci et al., 2020; Sharon, 2018; Talman et al., 2020). Different research found that education focused on E-I abilities and skills such as perceiving nonverbal signals, promoting logical thinking by using emotions, empathy, interpreting and managing emotion positively enhanced the E-I abilities among nursing students (Taylor et al., 2023; Budler et al., 2022; Fouad et al., 2018).

The Practice Based on Reflection:

Numerous researches demonstrated the benefits of incorporating reflective practices into nursing education. Practices based on reflection, like reflective writing, group discussions, and feedback sessions, have been proven to increase the E-I levels of nursing students and foster professional and personal growth (Taylor et al., 2023; Kaddoura, 2020; Fouad et al., 2018; Michelangelo, 2015). A quasi-experimental research study in Jordan revealed that intervention focused on group discussion and role-play had a noteworthy positive association between the E-I score and the degree of satisfaction. suggested that nursing students who obtained higher scores in the E-I assessment also boosted their level of satisfaction in clinical settings (Al-Faouri et al., 2014). Furthermore, E-I allows nursing students to form caring relationships with patients, provide compassionate care, and cope effectively with academic and clinical stresses. A systematic review conducted in 2020 further validated these findings that reflective practices augment nursing students' ability to understand and manage their emotions and the emotions of their colleagues and patients (Moustaka and Constandinis, 2020).

The Workshops Based on Interpersonal and Social Communication:

Strong communication influences the standard of patient care because nursing students with higher levels of communication skills can better connect with patients, eventually raising patient satisfaction. Numerous studies highlighted that interventions based on interpersonal communication skills, such as active listening and problem-resolution techniques, have positively increased the nursing students' teamwork abilities and overall E-I level (Taylor et al., 2023; Meng and Qi, 2018; Thomas and Natarajan, 2017). Furthermore, nursing students who participated in the workshop focused on social interaction and interpersonal communication have significantly increased their level of satisfaction and decline in their anxiety and burnout levels (Gomez et al., 2017). Additionally, another study corroborated these findings that education based on assertiveness, interpersonal communication skills, and conflict resolution strategies had a noteworthy positive impact on the overall level of E-I among nursing students (Taylor and Thomas, 2022).

The Learning Through Simulation:

E-I is a highly needed skill, considering coping styles in nursing students' training. Teaching methodologies based on simulation positively enhanced the E-I skills and competencies essential for nursing students, like promoting self-confidence, motivation, self-perception, efficacy, and emotion control (Ruiz et al., 2022; Alconero et al., 2018). Similarly, another study highlighted the effect of simulation-based learning on the E-I level of nursing students. The study result revealed that learning through simulations with debriefing sessions improved teamwork and emotional competencies and reduced stress levels among nursing students (Gurkova and Zelenikova, 2018). A pre-test post-test randomised control trial (RCT) conducted in 2023 showed that learning based on simulation increased the participants' E-I level, including the improvement of self-efficiency and problem-solving skills of nursing students (Cengiz et al., 2023). Another study found that nursing students engaged in learning based on simulation revealed improvement in their communication skills, better teamwork abilities and improved quality patient care (Smith and Jones, 2023). However, some studies highlighted no noteworthy variations in the participant's E-I level and suggested more significant interventional strategies and application methods. (Bsharat, 2024; Taylor et al., 2023; Mohamed, 2019).

Discussion:

The findings of this review article suggest that E-I have a significant role in the nursing profession. It is very rich from the result that E-I had a large part in both the nursing academia and clinical practice. E-I had a crucial impact on the overall capabilities of nursing students to motivate, communicate effectively and provide quality nursing care (Salovey and Mayer, 2020; Mayer et al., 2016). E-I skills are commonly accepted as a vital factor of nursing education, frequently referred to as the heart of nursing (Teskereci et al., 2020; Sharon, 2018; Talman et al., 2020). Considering the benefits and growing demand for E-I training in nursing. Nursing programmes should teach E-I and its practical skills because integrating emotional skills into nursing education is much more needed (Akerjordet and Severinsson, 2015). This will ensure that nursing students are adequately equipped to address challenges effectively (Goleman, 2015; Codier et al., 2014). Numerous research studies revealed that certain educational interventions significantly impacted nursing students' E-I levels. These interventions included reflective practices, mindfulness training, emotional skill training, simulation-based learning and interpersonal communication workshops (Gurkova and Zelenikova, 2018; Foster et al., 2018; Birks et al., 2017). For example, different studies highlighted that emotional skills interventions had a noteworthy positive association with nursing students' performance in both clinical and educational contexts and also enhanced the quality of interpersonal relationships. These interventions improved overall satisfaction and decreased depression among nursing students (Guo et al., 2019; Akerjordet and Severinsson, 2015). Likewise, interventions based on mindfulness have significantly improved stress management abilities and empathy levels, which can ultimately enhance the overall mental health of nursing students and improve quality nursing care (Taylor et al., 2022; Raut and Gupta, 2021). On the other hand, simulation-based learning like debriefing sessions, group discussions, feedback sessions and reflective writing have also been recognised as the best method for enhancing the E-I of nursing students. these interventions have significantly improved self-efficiency, problem-solving techniques and teamwork abilities. Which ultimately reduced stress levels and fostered personal and professional growth among nursing students, led enhanced quality patient care (Cengiz et al., 2023; Smith and Jones, 2023). Furthermore, the debriefing sessions, like reflections and feedback methods, can offer students a

chance to enhance their E-I level by effectively managing their emotions in stressful circumstances (Michelangelo, 2022; Gomez et al., 2017). In addition to this, if we talk specifically about reflective practices, it has been recognised as a very effective strategy in numerous studies. Research revealed that reflective writing practice and group discussion engagement could lead to self-awareness and emotional regulation (Kaddoura, 2020; Moustaka and Constandinis, 2020). Another study conducted in 2022 further validated and aligned these findings that reflective practices constantly augment nursing students' abilities and E-I over time (Budler et al., 2022). Nevertheless, many interventions have significantly positive results, but then again, the review clearly indicated areas that can be strengthened, such as the inconsistency in the intervention design, duration, and assessment methods in the current research studies. Standard and specialised methods for E-I intervention are needed. Future research should focus on developing special interventions and creative educational strategies to enhance the overall E-I abilities and focus on long-term effects (Taylor et al., 2022; Akerjordet and Severinsson, 2015). The instant effect has been highlighted in many studies, but a lack of longitudinal research has been noticed both in academic and clinical contexts (Codier et al., 2014). Despite the fruitful benefits of these E-I interventions, integrating E-I training into nursing education is also linked to the dedication of nursing educators and institutions (Kaddoura, 2020; Goleman, 2015). Therefore, it is very significant to include E-I training in nursing education and equip the nursing workforce with these crucial skills (Raut and Gupta, 2021; Foster et al., 2018).

Limitations:

We included only studies published in the last 10 years, from 2014 to 2024, to comprise recent findings. We included studies published in six data-based engines: Pub-Med, Bio-Med Central, Pak-MediNet, CABI, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. We may have missed studies meeting our inclusion criteria because they were published in journals rather than above. We narrowed our search to those studies that only focused on nursing students and those published in the English language, which may limit the generalisability of our findings and recommendations. One limitation is the different methods, study designs, and implementation of interventions among the reviewed studies. Furthermore, the interventions utilised numerous approaches, different durations and delivery styles, which may limit the direct comparison of their effectiveness and the application of the findings to the different contexts (Birks et al., 2017; Akerjordet and

Severinsson, 2015). Another curb is the limited longitudinal studies to explore the long-term effects of E-I interventions on nursing students, which may require further research. Moreover, the reviewed studies typically had low sample sizes and were from advanced countries. This may also limit the implementation of the findings to a wide range of cultures and demographic locations (Taylor et al., 2022; Moustaka and Constandinis, 2020). Therefore, further study may explore different populations and apply a specialised targeted intervention to improve the overall E-I level of students.

Conclusion:

Various methods and educational strategies have successfully boosted the E-I of nursing students. these strategies include mindfulness programs; Training focused on enhancing emotional skills, Practice based on reflection, Workshops based on interpersonal communication, and learning through simulation, effectively improving nursing students' E-I competencies. The findings suggest that enhanced E-I could positively impact nursing student's academic and clinical performance, as well as their resilience and stress levels. Which ultimately improved the quality of patient care. Nevertheless, the wide range of intervention designs and the scarcity of long-term research highlighted the importance of conducting more studies. A strong focus is on improving E-I interventions, and evaluating their lasting impact on nursing students is crucial.

Conflicts of Interest:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest

Acknowledgement:

The authors would like to thank Dr Ishrat Ishaq from (JMC) Javid Medical Complex Hazara, Kabal Swat, Dr Pamela Marshall (Dean), from Ziauddin University Faculty of Nursing and Midwifery, Mr. Javid Ali, Principal Ismail Nursing College Swat, Mr. Gohar Ali, Assistant Director Baqai Nursing College, Baqai Medical University and Mr. Meer Arsalan Khan, Psychologist (ANF) Anti Narcotic Force for providing guidance and assistance to the completion of this review article.

Funding:

The author(s) received no specific funding for this work.

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